

CONDITIONAL SENTENCES WITH MODAL VERBS

Abstract

Conditional sentences are used when we want to make a prediction about what might happen, would happen, or what we would like to happen. In English, most conditional sentences contain the word if. Many conditional sentences in English use a past tense verb. This usage is referred to as the "unreal past" because we are using the past tense but are not implying that something happened in the past. There are five ways to form conditional sentence types in English. Each of these sentence types will always consist of an if clause and a main clause. Many negative conditional sentences have a counterpart in the equivalent sentence structure of using "unless" instead of "if".

Conditionals in English are a type of sentence that express hypothetical, real, or possible events. Conditionals in English are divided into different types, and each of them has its own rules of formation and use. To feel comfortable among all types of conditional sentences, you will need a lot of practice. But first, you need to put on the shelves what each type of Conditionals looks like and in what cases they are used.

Conditional sentences with modal verbs are used to express possibilities, abilities, permissions, or obligations in different situations. They often convey a more nuanced meaning compared to simple conditional sentences. In the article we will look at in what situations is preferable to use modal verbs in conditional sentences.

Key words: conditionals, modal verbs, imperative mood, main clause, hypothetical, obligation

Conditional sentences consist of two parts: the condition itself (condition) and the consequence of this condition (the main part of the sentence). The consequence states the action that should occur if the condition is met. The meaning of each part can also be determined by a formal feature: the condition most often begins with the word *if*.

The two parts of the sentence can follow in any order: you can say the condition first, then the consequence, or vice versa. The order does not affect the meaning of the message. However, here a syntactic rule is evident: the order affects the placement of the comma in the sentence. If we put *if* clause first, we usually separate the clauses with comma, especially one clause is quite long. If the consequence comes first, then a comma is not needed.

If I see Jackson tomorrow, I will tell him about his illness.

I will tell Jackson about his illness if I see him tomorrow.

The part with *if* condition is a subordinate clause, so questions in such constructions are asked about the main part of the sentence, that is, about the consequence.

Will you tell Jackson about his illness if you see him tomorrow?

There are five types of conditional sentences in English. They differ in the nature of the conditions in the sentence and the correlation of the event with reality and are formed using different grammatical rules.

Zero Conditional

First Conditional

Second Conditional

Third Conditional

Mixed Conditional

The choice of one of these types is determined by two parameters. First, the speaker needs to determine whether the situation is real, or whether the condition

can only be fulfilled in an unreal world. Second, determine the tense for each part of the sentence. In conditional sentences, the tense in the condition and the consequence are independent of each other and each is determined by the meaning of the situation. For example, when it comes to a real condition, about the order of things in the world, then simple verb tenses are enough for the constructions. When the sentence refers to unreal situations that do not happen in life, the subjunctive mood appears in the constructions. In this case, the unreal event can refer to the present and future or to the past.

When it comes to the most likely and realistic condition, the zero condition comes first. If we talk about sentences in English, this type of conditional sentences describes sentences that are most likely to occur. They are used to describe scientific facts, habits and regular actions, general truths. In addition, the zero condition is used to describe rules and causal relationships.

As sentences with the condition of present time, this type applies to all time, and not only to the present or the future. They express a fact or situation that usually happens in real life and is always or usually true, regardless of time.

Modal verbs can occur in both parts of a sentence, in all conditional sentences.

The main part of the Zero Conditional often uses modal verbs: *can / may / should / must*.

If I finish my homework, we can go for a walk.

In First Conditional sentences modal verbs can be used:

can — to express ability;

may — to express permission;

must, should — to express obligation.

If you don't have your purse with you, you may pay it next time.

If you want to travel around the world, you can go on an excursion.

If you don't have a sleeping bag, you may take mine.

If the sea level starts rising quickly, we must act together.

If we want to help homeless people, we should make special shelters for them.

First Conditional is a conditional sentence that expresses a real or very probable situation in the present or future. In First Conditional sentences the subordinate clause always uses the Present Simple tense, and in the main clause, depending on the situation, the Future Simple, imperative mood or modal verbs can, must, may, etc. with an infinitive without the particle to can be used.

If you like this t-shirt and trousers, we can buy them.

You may stay at home next week if you are feeling bad.

Mary must get up early if she wants this job.

If you miss the last bus, you will catch the taxi.

If you miss the last bus, you can catch the taxi.

If you miss the last bus, you must catch the taxi.

Second Conditional sentence expressing an unreal situation in the present. The subordinate clause expresses an imaginary situation that contradicts the facts in the present, and therefore is impossible or unlikely in the present or future.

The Second Conditional always contains the Past Simple and a modal verb - these are the distinguishing features of sentences with this meaning. Modal verbs are used to show how unrealistic what is said is:

You would be happy if you rode a real dragon.

The Second Conditional can be useful when we talk about something undesirable.

He would be very angry if he knew.

In Second Conditional sentences, the Past Simple is always used in the subordinate clause, and the verb were (not was) is used for all persons. In the main part of such sentences, the modal verbs would, could, might with the infinitive of the verb without the particle to are used. In these sentences, the conjunction if cannot be replaced by when.

If I were him, I would never forget it.

If Russel were rich, would he move to Italy with his family?

Michael could be happy if he married Alice.

My friends might walk in the park if the weather were nice.

The choice between would, might and could depends on the shade of meaning you want to put into the statement. Compare:

If it stopped raining, we would go to the forest.

If it stopped raining, we might go to the forest.

If it stopped raining, we could go to the forest.

Third Conditional is a conditional sentence that expresses an unreal situation in the past and its unreal consequences, i.e. this situation never happened. Most often, conditional constructions of the 3rd conditional convey annoyance, criticism, reproach for something not done in the past.

In Third Conditional sentences the subordinate if-clause uses the Past Perfect tense, and sometimes the

Past Perfect Continuous, and in the main clause - the modal verbs would, could, might and the perfect infinitive without the particle to. In such sentences, the conjunction if cannot be replaced by when.

You could have passed your exam if you had studied harder.

If mother had asked me for help, I would have helped her.

If you hadn't been walking for so long, we might have arrived to the cinema on time.

Mixed Conditionals are conditional sentences in which the situations or actions in the subordinate and main clauses refer to different tenses. Only second and third conditional sentences can be mixed with each other. There are two types of mixed conditional sentences.

In the first type of mixed sentences, the condition in the if-clause refers to the past tense, and the result in the main clause refers to the present. In this case, the if-clause uses the Past Perfect tense (as in the third conditional), and the main clause uses the modal verbs would, could, might with a simple infinitive without the particle to (as in the second conditional).

If I had got that work, I couldn't be nervous now.

If we had taken an umbrella, we wouldn't be wet now.

They might be still happy together if they hadn't moved.

In the second type of mixed sentences, the condition in the if-clause does not refer to a specific time, but is a general constant characteristic of something. However, the result or consequences of this in the main clause occurred in the past. In this case, the if-clause uses the Past Simple tense (as in the second conditional), and the main clause uses the modal verbs would, could, might with the perfect infinitive without the particle to (as in the third conditional).

I would appreciate it if you would send us any information you have on this.

If I spoke English, I could have been selected to this competition.

If I weren't afraid of father, I might haven't passed my exams yet.

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